

Preparation of Ce³⁺-doped phosphors by sintering of glass microspheres

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ABSTRACT

In the present work we report on preparation and preliminary characterisation of compact samples prepared by hot pressing of glass microspheres powders in the Ce³⁺ doped Y₂O₃-Al₂O₃ system with different ratio of YAG to Al₂O₃ phase in a composite. First, the thermal properties of prepared glass microspheres were studied by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Based on the thermal behaviour, the hot press conditions were selected and luminescent properties of prepared compacts have been investigated.

The composition of prepared Ce³⁺-doped glasses is derived from the corresponding un-doped system by equimolar substitution of Y₂O₃ by Ce₂O₃ and is summarised in Tab. 1. The concentration of Ce³⁺ ions in a glass was kept at constant level of 1.0 at. %.

Tab. 1: Theoretical composition of prepared glass

Sample ^{&}	Glass composition			Ce ³⁺ (at.%)	Ce ³⁺ in YAG (at.%) [#]
	Y ₂ O ₃ (mol.%)	Al ₂ O ₃ (mol.%)	Ce ₂ O ₃ (mol.%)		
30% YAG : 70% Al ₂ O ₃ (eut.)	22.64	76.86	0.50	1.00	3.48
50% YAG : 50% Al ₂ O ₃	18.25	81.25	0.50	1.00	2.00
70% YAG : 30% Al ₂ O ₃	25.75	73.75	0.50	1.00	1.42

[&]Denotes composition of YAG/Al₂O₃ phase in the whole sample in mol.%; [#]Recalculated under assumption that all Ce³⁺ ions are hosted in YAG phase after crystallization (heat treatment).

The prepared glass microspheres of given compositions were found to be XRD amorphous within the detection limit of the XRD diffractometer. The DSC analysis revealed the two exothermic effects, the first one at temperatures around 940°C and the second effect, ranging from 965°C up to 1060°C, that is significantly dependent on the composition of the glass. Both effects correspond to the crystallization of the YAG phase, as documented also by high temperature XRD [1]. The Al₂O₃ phase as corundum start to crystallize over 1300°C [1]. The *T_g* temperature estimated from DSC data was found to be around 890°C.

The bulk glass from microspheres with eutectic composition was prepared at temperature 840°C with dwell time 0 min, applying the pressure of 40MPa. The glass-ceramic samples with YAG crystals embedded in residual glass matrix were prepared at temperatures 1000°C and 1100°C with the dwell time 30 and 60 min. The yellow colour of the consolidated bulk samples typical for the YAG:Ce phosphor was observed. It should be noted, that for hot-press experiments, glass microspheres without any treatment in reducing atmosphere was used.

The excitation (PLE) and emission (PL) spectra of the glass bulk sample with eutectic composition is depicted on Fig. 1A. The excitation spectrum was monitored at wavelength 430 nm. The strong absorption with maxima at 355 nm can be ascribed to 4f-5d transition in Ce³⁺ ions. The emission spectrum of the glass compact recorded under UV excitation at 350 nm exhibits broad emission band in spectral range of 365-550 nm with the emission maximum at 430 nm. This emission corresponds to the 5d→²F_{5/2} and 5d→²F_{7/2} transitions that are not clearly resolved as in the other Ce³⁺ doped systems with blue emission [2]. This is most likely due to the close energy of the 4f (²F_{5/2}, ²F_{7/2}) ground states in Ce³⁺ ions in the yttrium aluminate glass; Ce³⁺ with 4f¹ electron configuration has two ground states of ²F_{5/2} and ²F_{7/2} due to the spin-orbital coupling. The blue emission point to the weaker crystal field strength around Ce³⁺ ions in prepared glasses compared to the crystal field strength around Ce³⁺ ions in YAG phase (green-yellow emission).

Fig. 1: (A) The excitation and emission (PL) spectra of sample with composition 30% YAG-70% Al₂O₃ (eutectic composition) prepared by hot-press of glass microspheres at 840°C/0 min. (B) The PL spectra of sample with composition 30% YAG-70% Al₂O₃ prepared by hot-press of glass microspheres at different temperature and dwell time. Inset represent emission spectra under sample excitation by UV and blue light. (C) The PL spectra of sample with different composition prepared by hot-press of glass microspheres at 1000°C/60 min.

The PL emission spectra ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 455 \text{ nm}$) of hot-pressed samples with eutectic composition at different temperatures and dwell time are depicted in Fig. 1B. A typical broad emission band centred at $\sim 550 \text{ nm}$ is seen in spectra of samples. The PL emission curves can be deconvoluted into two broad Gaussian bands centred at $\sim 527 \text{ nm}$ (peak 1) and $\sim 577 \text{ nm}$ (peak 2). These two peaks correspond to the typical $5d^1-4f^1$ ($^2F_{5/2}$) and $5d^1-4f^1$ ($^2F_{7/2}$) transitions of Ce^{3+} ion, the energy difference between the two energy levels is $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to of the spin-orbital coupling in crystal-field [3]. The PL emission intensity depends on the treatment temperature. As the temperature increases from 1000°C to 1100°C , the PL emission intensity significantly increases. The increase of emission intensity with treatment temperature is due to the improvement of crystallinity of samples; most likely more Ce^{3+} doped YAG crystalline phase is formed in the residual glass matrix. The PL spectra of compact samples prepared from different compositions of starting glass sintered at $1000^\circ\text{C}/60 \text{ min}$ are depicted in Fig. 1C. The emission intensity increases with expected concentration of Ce^{3+} ions in YAG phase for 1.42 and 2.0 at.%, than for concentration 3.48 at.% decreases, most likely due to the energy transfer between Ce^{3+} ions and non-radiative transitions, the effect well known as concentration quenching. The testing of mechanical properties and microstructural study of compact bulk phosphors is currently in progress.

Keywords: Ce^{3+} , phosphors, solid state lighting, pc-WLED.

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566. This work was also supported by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under the contract No. APVV-17-0049 and by grant VEGA 1/0527/18.

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